

THEORETICAL BASIS OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE POTENTIAL OF PEDAGOGICAL STAFF IN THE CONDITIONS OF EDUCATION INFORMATION

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Abstract: *The article considers the possibilities of creating a pedagogical creative environment for the formation and development of the scientific potential of teaching staff and to form the need to further advance in self-knowledge, creative self-development, to form an objective self-assessment of the individual.*

Keywords: *creative potential, pedagogical creative environment, education, worldview.*

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada professor-o'qituvchilarning ilmiy salohiyatini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish uchun shaxsning pedagogik ijodiy muhitni yaratish va o'z-o'zini bilishda, ijodiy o'zini-o'zi rivojlantirishda ilgarilab borish zarurligini, shaxsning ob'yektiv o'zini o'zi baholashni shakllantirish imkoniyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ijodiy salohiyat, pedagogik ijodiy muhit, ta'lim, dunyoqarash.*

Аннотация: *В статье рассматривается возможности создания педагогической креативной среды формирования и развития научного потенциала педагогических кадров и сформировать потребность в дальнейшем продвигаться в самопознании, творческом саморазвитии, сформировать у личности объективную самооценку.*

Ключевые слова: *креативный потенциал, педагогическая креативная среда, образование, мировоззрение.*

The most important task in the formation and development of creative potential in the system of continuous education is the creation of a comfortable social and humane environment, the democratization and humanization of education. A favorable psychological climate is characterized by an atmosphere of mutual respect, friendliness, delicacy, creates comfort and conditions for creative work, and reveals the potential of the individual. In order to form and develop creative potential, it is necessary to combine subject-cognitive and creative activities. Purposeful training of

flexibility of thinking, associativity, the use of fantasy, intuition, imagination, research teaching methods - all this contributes to the development of creative potential [2].

At the same time, the main requirement of modern education is to become humanistically oriented, to consider a person as the main value, to be aimed at the development of the individual. This approach makes any forms, methods, technologies of education not an end in itself, but considers them in the context of one of the main tasks of education - to provide the most favorable conditions for self-development of the individual. Agreeing with the existence of creativity as a dynamic quality of a person, it is necessary to understand the process of its emergence and formation in the process of professional training of a person. So, for the manifestation of creativity, a free, relaxed atmosphere is needed. Achievement motivation, competition, motivation of social approval block the self-actualization of the individual, hinder the manifestation of its creative capabilities. In this regard, the development of creative potential occurs under the influence of the creative microenvironment and the imitation of creative behavior forms a system of relevant components that are transformed into creative potential [1].

However, there are several directions in this approach. Druzhinin V., Khazratova N. consider the following necessary for the development of creative potential:

- the absence of regulation of subject activity, in particular - the absence of a model, regulated behavior;
- the presence of a positive sample of creative activity, the creation of conditions for its inheritance;
- planning and avoiding manifestations of aggressive and destructive behavior;
- social approval of creative behavior.

This means that the development of creative potential is not reduced to the accumulation of experience, but is presented as a structural change in the operational composition. Creative potential develops due to processes similar to "balancing", which are triggered when a cognitive-emotional conflict occurs [4]. Galperin developed a developmental method based on social interaction. The idea of social learning is that we are able to learn by observing the behavior of other people and taking it as a model. Patterns of creative behavior can form a certain approach to solving problems, to determining the scope of tasks. Patterns of creative behavior can form a certain approach to solving problems, to determining the scope of tasks. The idea of a socially active conflict suggests that the interaction between subjects with different views on issues and different strategies for solving the problem leads to the emergence of internal conflict and disequilibrium, which gives impetus to the creative development of the individual. At the same time, not every environment becomes a development environment. This process is influenced only by the conditions under which a person enters into one or another real connection. In this case, everyone creates their own educational space as a space for entering the culture in accordance with their

individual characteristics. The environment affects the development of the individual through activities that are learning, education. In this regard, in the scientific literature such a concept as "educational environment" is considered. Kovalenko A. considers the educational environment as a system of influences and conditions for the formation of a personality according to the provided model, as well as opportunities for its development, which are in the social and spatial-subject environment. Bershadsky M.E., Guzeeva V.V. consider the educational environment as a diverse multicultural education, individual for each student, an environment for building one's own "I", which ensures the creation of conditions for the actualization of the student's inner world, his personal growth, self-realization, the formation of his self-consciousness [3].

The educational environment of a modern educational institution as a set of spiritual and material conditions for the functioning of an educational institution that ensures the self-development of a free and active person, the realization of creative potential. The educational environment acts as a functional and spatial association of subjects of education, between which close diverse group relationships are established, and can be considered as a model of the sociocultural space in which the formation of a personality takes place. The theoretical analysis of the scientific literature allowed us to determine that for the full influence of the pedagogically creative environment in order to form the creative potential, certain requirements must be met:

- creating a free atmosphere;
- high degree of uncertainty and problems;
- continuity and succession;
- subject-information enrichment of educational material;
- creation of an equal position "teacher - student".
- round table methods, seminars (interdisciplinary, problematic, thematic).

In order to form creative potential as comprehensively and harmoniously developed personalities, capable of self-development and self-improvement, it is also necessary to introduce a personality-oriented approach. After all, given that creativity is a quality of a person, without taking into account the personal approach to the formation of creative potential, in our opinion, it is impossible. Therefore, its observance will contribute to the formation of all components of the creative potential. In turn, a creative educational environment should not only enable each student at each educational level to develop the initial creative potential, but also form the need to further advance in self-knowledge, creative self-development, and form an objective self-esteem in the individual. The main requirements for a creative educational environment are a high degree of uncertainty and problematicness, continuity and succession, student acceptance and inclusion in active educational activities. Thus, the pedagogical creative environment is an artificially created atmosphere of professional training of students on the basis of equality, freedom in order to initiate and maintain an active search process, develop individual independence, and form creative potential

[1]. Given the specifics of creative potential, the formation of this quality becomes possible if we create a relative equality of positions "teacher - student" in the process of continuous education (joint mastery of knowledge by the teacher and the student). The teacher only guides the student on the path to mastering knowledge, and does not present the material in finished form, so it is perceived by the student as the result of his own work.

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